

Society and Sustainable Development

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Introduction

Sustainable development is the idea that human societies must live and meet their needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland Report, 1987) Sustainable development means attaining a balance between environmental protection and human economic development and between the present and future needs. It means equity in development and sectoral actions across space and time. It requires an integration of economic, social and environmental approaches towards development. In Vellore Citizen Welfare Forum V. Union of India and M.C. Mehta V. Union of India, it was observed that the balance between environmental protection and developmental activities could only be maintained by strictly following the principle of sustainable development. This is a development strategy that caters to the needs of the present without negotiating the ability of upcoming generations to satisfy their needs. The strict observance of sustainable development will put us on a path that ensures development while protecting the environment, a path that works for all peoples and for all generations. It is a guarantee to the present and a bequest to the future. All environmental related developmental activities should benefit more people while maintaining the environmental balance. This could be ensured only by the strict adherence of sustainable development without which life of coming generations will be in jeopardy.

Society and Sustainable Development

Sociology is at the core when building a sustainable future. For centuries, sociologists have contributed to the study of key developmental changes facing societies from poverty, inequality, migration, industrial relations and economic development in early modernization to gender equality and diversity, urban life, health and wellbeing, education and climate justice in the globalized era. Sociologists engage each of the United Nations Sustainable Development goals with the scientific investigation of the social causes and consequences of human behavior, social change and social life (ASA). Humanity is reaching another turning point in history, signaled by the recent COP26 climate deal that initiates the phasing out of fossil fuels. Sociology is the discipline offering theoretical foundation, transdisciplinary connections, and cutting edge research methodology to envision a pathway for transition to a post-carbon society. It helps you to understand and develop ways to make the community you are living in more sustainable.

A Unique Stream

Society and Sustainable Development (SSD) is a new stream introduced in 2022-23 under the sociology programme (Non-JUPAS Senior Year Admissions) in collaboration with the Earth System Science Programme and the Gender Studies Programme. New Senior year admission places will be assigned to the sociology programmes to admit

students with an appropriate Higher Diploma/Associate Degree from a recognized institution. The SSD stream addresses the complex nature of sustainable development through bridging social science and science, resulting in two unique knowledge clusters and the diversity cluster. Students admitted to the SSD stream will follow a specified study path from the start, which allows them to study selected courses from across the three programmes mentioned above. Students will first undergo foundation training in sociology, and then proceed to 1. expand scientific knowledge and technician skills essential to the study of global climate change; 2. Advance social science knowledge in the area of gender and diversity study, and explore the relevant policy making process to achieve sustainable development goals.

Structure of SSD Stream

Students in the SSD stream are required to complete a minimum of 61 units of courses as follows: Foundation in sociology-30 units from the sociology programme, Elective courses, Career Prospectus. Students completing the SSD stream will benefit from transdisciplinary knowledge and skill sets essential to meet the key challenges of the 21st century. The integrated academic training from the three collaborating CUKH programmes allows you to think beyond a single discipline and to seek innovative solutions for sustainable development from both social science and science knowledge

domains. The SSD stream offers three kinds of literacy training that help to build your carrier.

Climate Literacy

In face of climate change and as nations further their efforts to institutionalize net zero-emission targets, 'Climate Literacy' becomes an important asset to both governments, private and NGO sectors. 'Climate literacy' is an understanding of the mutual influence between climate, individual and society, and the ability to understand the Earth's climate system, to know how to access or generate scientifically credible information about climate to communicate climate knowledge in a meaningful way and to make an informed and responsible decision with climatic action coalition for Climate Education Policy. Our climate knowledge cluster aims to help you to master climate literacy.

Diversity Literacy

The increasingly interconnected global village of the 21st century requires one to possess the ability to think critically about complex social issues over identity, power and difference. Learning how knowledge, skills and practice of inclusion and equity shapes lives and workplaces become essential to navigate multicultural setting and to appreciate the cultural assumption of others. People who are diversity literate value differences and recognize how it influences lives, and develop the potential to set up good governance for inclusion and social equity (Department of Philosophy, University of Louisville). Our society cluster and diversity cluster helps you to develop such soft skills like skills, critical thinking and problem-solving for developing good governance.

Computational Literacy

Computational thinking is a core asset for graduates who wish to develop a better carrier in the age of industrial 4.0 selected sociology courses will help you master to computational method to analyze and solve complex social research problems, drawing large-scale data from social media, dynamic network, real-time digitized and administrative records, and social simulations. Computational training from earth system science will enable you to understand and build climate and basic emission models. These are skill sets for you to attract the attention of private or public

organizations looking to strengthen their environmental governance or to solve problems with computational methods. According to the Global Employability Ranking and Survey 2021 (GEURS, Times Higher Education). CUKH graduates rank third among universities in Hong Kong in terms of employability. GEURs also identified 'Soft Skills and Digital Literacy' as the most important consideration factor for employers, followed by specialization (Technical and Research Expertise) our SSD stream will help prepare you for a job market that increasingly looks for talents with SDGs knowledge and technical expertise.

Conclusion

The build a sustainable society, a delicate balance between current needs and future needs has to be teacher. In the past, the law of nature ensured this balance. Today, the law of nature still applies. However, with our capability to utilize the reserved resources, human beings have a choice to make. We could continue to use up all the reserved resources and let out children suffer the consequence of resource starvation or we could aggressively move away from non-renewable resources and put ourselves on a sustainable footing once and for all our ability to think coupled with our greed has led us on a collision course with nature. If we continue on this could also be made possible by remaining source and signs of unsustainability in a long run perspective.

References

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